

**UNDERSTANDING THE RECOMMENDER VALIDATION STEPS IN AN
ITERATIVE DESIGN PROCESS**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528775>

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Abstract: *On the Internet, where the number of choices is overwhelming, it is necessary to filter, prioritize, and efficiently deliver relevant information in order to alleviate the problem of information overload, which has created a potential problem for many Internet users. Recommender systems solve this problem by searching a large amount of dynamically generated information to provide users with personalized content and services. This article explores the various features of recommender systems to serve as a compass for research and practice in the field of recommender systems.*

Key words: *validation of the algorithms, validation of the recommendations, dataset, collecting user, subjective qualitative evaluation diary studies.*

Introduction: Recommender systems (RS) are software tools and methods that suggest items that may be useful to the user. Suggestions relate to various decision-making processes, such as what products to buy, what music to listen to, or what online news to read. "Item" is a generic term used to refer to what the system recommends to users. RS usually focuses on a specific element type, and accordingly its design, its graphical user interface, and the main recommendation method used to generate recommendations are customized to provide useful and efficient suggestions for that particular element type.

RS is primarily intended for individuals who lack the personal experience or expertise to appreciate the potentially overwhelming number of alternative elements that a website, for example, has to offer. An example is a book recommendation system that helps users choose a book to read. The popular Amazon.com website uses RS to personalize the online store for each shopper. Because recommendations are usually personalized, different users or groups of users receive different suggestions. In addition, there are also non-personalized

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recommendations. They are much easier to create and are usually featured in magazines or newspapers. Typical examples include top 10 books, CDs, etc. While they can be useful and effective in certain situations, these types of non-personalized recommendations are not usually considered in MS research.

In their simplest form, personalized recommendations are offered as ranked lists of items. In performing this ranking, RSs try to predict what the most suitable products or services are, based on the user's preferences and constraints. In order to complete such a computational task, RSs collect from users their preferences, which are either explicitly expressed, e.g., as ratings for products, or are inferred by interpreting user actions. For instance, a RS may consider the navigation to a particular product page as an implicit sign of preference for the items shown on that page. RSs development initiated from a rather simple observation: individuals often rely on recommendations provided by others in making routine, daily decisions. For example it is common to rely on what one's peers recommend when selecting a book to read; employers count on recommendation letters in their recruiting decisions; and when selecting a movie to watch, individuals tend to read and rely on the movie reviews that a film critic has written and which appear in the newspaper they read.

Validation of the Algorithms

Many experimental works have demonstrated the usefulness of testing the recommender method on existing datasets such as MovieLens, Netflix15, etc. experience, such datasets are useful for understanding the behavior of the algorithm; sometimes they need to be transformed and enriched in order to be usable (e.g. enrich MovieLens with IMDB16 data). Experiments with datasets have been extensively researched in the literature. For example, provides a very exhaustive list of metrics that can be calculated. In addition, they allow for an objective comparison with other methods based on the characteristics and information available in the collections, and can be especially useful when large groups of users are required. Such The score also allows you to adjust a number of algorithm personalization options, eg. distance metrics to calculate the similarity between the user profile and piece of content. These methods are widely described in the literature and therefore not detailed here.

At this particular stage of testing the algorithm on the available data set, the function dependencies and influence graph determined by the method described if the recommender dataset changes. environment (data, user, application) compared to the final target system. This the graph should help interpret the results of the algorithms and determine how far Algorithm tuning and testing should go. Indeed,

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if the properties of the environment are really close to those of the target end system, it might be worth adjusting it. algorithms as far as possible. But if significant differences were analyzed between the experimental environment and the target environment, this phase experiments with existing datasets should probably be as short as possible and should mainly focus on debugging rather than slightly improving the accuracy of recommendations. Many scientific works are devoted to improving accuracy of algorithms, but even if the recommendation algorithm provides good accuracy results, it's still with respect to data instance and user considered and associated with the model dataset. Therefore it is very important understand the importance of the features of environmental models and their interdependence in order to correctly interpret the results of an assessment compared to a standardized one data set. For example, when we move from television data to news data, the behavior the user is no longer the same, and the data does not have the same dynamics. In such a case, spend too much time tweaking the algorithm to improve TV data set accuracy is definitely a waste of time.

Validation of the Recommendations

While there are technical strategies for mathematically evaluating the accuracy promoted products offered by the recommender, litmus test for ensuring measures Likely performance and satisfaction in the field is ultimately achieved by evaluating all areas of the recommender system with end users, with a focus on improving performance and increasing end user satisfaction.

The key to evaluating any interactive system is to follow a user-centric approach. This means early, iterative and frequent evaluation based on changes and improvements have been made. This creates some problems. In fact, as discussed earlier, recommenders are rarely at the forefront of development, but instead are an integrated part of a much larger product or system. The general scenarios are: the development of a larger host system is done on a different time scale. to the recommendation system. This situation creates problems for assessing basic recommender technology leaving no room for collecting user preferences on the basis of which you can create a user profile or a way to provide recommendations to users.

These considerations often lead to an evaluation of the user experience. aspects of the recommender (data collection processes and representation) is separated from the underlying mechanism, at least as long as both systems achieve prototype integration. In terms of evaluation, this can sometimes makes a lot of sense, e.g. preventing distortion of research results competing negative or positive

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responses to other design areas. There are many possible methods in the user assessment toolkit that can be deployed to study the development of recommenders. Some Useful Selective Techniques are presented below, along with an indication of when and in what context they are best used. Each of them has been used in real projects and is based on our experience. conducting user research in the field of recommender systems.

Card Sorting

Card sorting is not only a method of evaluation, but also a useful formative design. research tool. It is used to create taxonomies of items based on naturalistic mental models that users use for relationships between content or concepts. the method basically consists of asking users to sort a set of cards, each of which depicts a content item or sub-classification grouped based on similarit. The resulting sorted groups from multiple users can be analyzed using cluster analysis to find common patterns in user classification and build association dendrogram. The time and complexity of this analysis can be significantly reduced when using one of the software tools such as EZsort from IBM.

We have used this method in the study of distance functions for the television genre. classification. Although there are many metadata structures in this area, it is very difficult to without testing with users to see if a particular genre is perceived as more similar to any other genre more than others. For example, one result from the study found that users categorized a number of different genres as close to each other due to the perception of all of them as representing easier viewing. Genres included. such as game shows, comedies and soap operas. This was in contrast to the more actual genres of content classified as less similar, such as news and documentaries. This the information has been integrated into the development of the algorithm to improve accuracy recommendations.

The value of this exercise is that the similarity measures of content items are based on taxonomy created by real users rather than artificial structures created by programmers or engineers. This method also reveals the subjective relative distances between individual categories. These two factors increase the likelihood recommendations are perceived as relevant and accurate in terms of User. Due to its advantages in building basic algorithms, this tool best used during formative development.

Subjective qualitative evaluation

This method aims to evaluate the level of accuracy and satisfaction achieved recommendation engine from the end user's point of view. Main advantage this method is universal: it is a qualitative method that can be used as soon as the

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system is capable of making recommendations even if the ancillary data collection and recommendation presentation components do not yet exist. It can equally be used for evaluate fully implemented systems. The process is based on a subjective assessment A useful way to apply the method is to either enter the facilitator or have the participant complete a standardized questionnaire. Every recommendation generated for the user, presented in the questionnaire and asked a series of questions regarding the user's opinion about it. Basic concept of the method consists of three steps.

1. Collecting user data to create user profiles: amount of data to collect is a function of recommender performance. However, it may equally be appropriate to create samples of participants as part of a study. from which different amounts of information are intercepted to represent different typical usage patterns at certain points in time, for example two weeks later. This allows the influence of the recommender learning curve on users' perceptions of accuracy and satisfaction to be analyzed. The ease with which data can be obtained from users, again a function of the maturity and design of the recommender. If the system is on the design phase in which the preference data collection functions function, then consideration may be given to their use in the study. This is especially true in systems where implicit usage data needs to be collected, as this can be very it is difficult to get this type of data directly from users by other means. obviously, it is very important that the development team can access the real user. Hence use of previously collected user data (for example, in the form of web analytics) not applicable from a direct evaluation point of view. Collection of implicit data from zero requires recruiting participants for longer-term controlled trials. This requires the use of methods such as video surveillance or remote monitoring of usage in to collect accurate preference data that can then be extracted and applied to implicit learning rules. This can be a time-consuming research activity, but also provide additional benefits of collecting information about real users and new examples uses, which in turn stimulate innovation. In contrast, explicit data collection is much easier. simulate without a running system. Collecting feedback via email or a paper survey form is a good method. The example we used was simple spreadsheet. Users were asked to rate forty pieces of content on an explicit scale that was suggested for the finished system. Fifty participants selected. are dialed remotely over the Internet, and the survey is sent via email. Users just completed their responses and returned them to the design team.

2. Generation of recommendations. The preference data returned by the participants is extracted from the survey responses and encoded for input into the

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recommendation engine. An important consideration when providing individualized recommendations is to track user ownership of data and responses to reviews throughout the study. First, get permission from users to keep their information for the duration of the study. Give each member an ID and use that number on each document throughout the evaluation process. Save securely participant details throughout the study period, for which the participant ID may be resolved. Finally, make sure that participants' sensitive personal data is destroyed after the study and anonymization of the study results. This simple process ensures user privacy (and data protection).

3. Presentation of recommendations: once recommendations for each individual user have been generated then they need to be given back to participants for evaluation. The questions to ask participants in the questionnaire really depend upon the goals of the recommender. Three common user perspectives on the recommendations that are likely to be of interest are:

- Does the recommendation match their preferences?
- Is the recommendation of interest?
- Would they be satisfied in a system that delivered such a recommendation?

It is important that questions are first framed around specific recommended items, rather than the list of recommendations as a whole, because they are less likely to provide insight that can be used to improve the recommender. Receiving the information on individual elements allows you to identify weaknesses and errors in the design of the recommender. identified. For the TV recommendation project we were working on, this allowed us to understand why a successful recommender received a small number of extremely low satisfaction scores with outliers. Investigation outliers revealed recommendations for content in a foreign language, not defined by metadata. The design team has made a correction to more reasonably identify and process this type of foreign language content and solve the dissatisfaction problem. Data analysis can provide detailed pictures of likely user satisfaction. It can also allow for direct comparisons between competing systems, which can be used either for benchmarking purposes or fed back into design direction decisions.

Diary studies

When the referrer enters the field, how can information be gathered about development success in the medium and long term? Collection of usage data metrics do not reflect subjective motivation, enjoyment, or frustration with use system. An important consideration for recommenders is that such systems can

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have long learning curves with changing user experience over long periods of time use. In such cases, an analysis of the overall experience of living with the system can be more interesting than snapshots of satisfaction. Diary research can usually be done from a week to months, depending on the system under study and accessibility to interested users. Diary research as a method particularly well suited to mobile contexts where direct observation or monitoring becomes logistically difficult. We recently used this method for a study related to to assess the impact of different contexts of use on the choice of video content on heterogeneous mobile devices, where remote user registration was not possible. The method proved to be very useful in identifying specific user pain points.

Diary is in fact a very well establish method in many areas of social research. The method relies upon a user to create a self-reported record of their day-to-day interactions with the system of interest (it relates to real user contexts described in their own words). The insight from such data can be integrated to improve systems already in use to uncover user requirements and contextual use issues for the next generation of development. However, in terms of logistics the method does have possible pitfalls to be considered:

- recruitment and retention of users: it can often be difficult to recruit participants for longer duration studies, and even more difficult to retain them;

- non-reporting or false reporting of information in the diary: completing diary entries takes effort and engagement which can be difficult for users to sustain over the whole duration of a study

To successfully conduct a diary study, it is very important to maintain contact with participants. Regular face-to-face or telephone debriefing encourages users to support their diaries, instilling expectations in investigators and allowing the investigator to track the collected data and request incidents or comments closer to once events are reported. Such strategies can be used to identify critical usage incidents that have led to episodes of user satisfaction or dissatisfaction. While this list is by no means exhaustive, this set of techniques has significant utility throughout the development process, from the early stages of design, through prototyping, and finally pre-release and post-release.

Conclusion

A recommendation system is an information service system that connects users and projects: on the one hand, it helps users discover potential projects of interest; on the other hand, it helps project providers to deliver projects to users who are interested in it. The recommendation system is a powerful system that can

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add value to the company or business. In the future, it will continue to be researched and developed to bring a better experience to users.

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